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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“BUILDING A LEGACY OF INTEGRITY: A REFLECTION ON ETHICAL VALUES”

Warren Buffet once said, “It takes 20 years to build a reputation and only 5 minutes to ruin it.” This is the very reason why understanding Ethical Values is important; it’s a reflection of who we are. It’s a core principle each of us must practice every day. We are blessed to have this as one of the major subjects in Doctor of Education. Its objective is to give us a deep understanding of ethical theories and principles, helping us analyze complex problems and learn how to promote integrity and responsibility in our academic and professional lives. It is essential for doctorate students and researchers, since it develops us a strong ethical basis for our professions and promote its value to others.

Before deciding to enroll in doctoral, I already have insights about ethical values. As the discussion continues, more essential topics and learnings were added to my closet of knowledge. I learned the importance of practicing academic integrity, whether or not anyone knows. It’s the core of our academic work and the reason our readers trust us. Being ethical isn’t only about knowing the right thing to do; it’s about doing it, even when it’s difficult.

Several topics were discussed during the semester. We covered the principles of academic integrity and the different types of academic misconduct. Plagiarism is defined as the use of another person’s words or ideas without giving them credit. We also discussed data falsification, which is the changing of facts or data to achieve a desired effect, and data fabrication, which is the making up data or outcomes. I learned that these misconducts are more than just mistakes; they have the power to destroy a person’s reputation and professional career. Once our reputation has been damaged, it is difficult to repair.

Beyond these ethics, my understanding of integrity expands. It thought me that being honest in everything is the most precious asset we could ever have. My understanding deepen that be ethical not just because of fear of getting exposed but to appreciate for the value of our own work and effort. When we work hard and follow ethical guidelines, we are building our reputation hand in hand. Every article we write and every source we properly acknowledge contributes to a legacy of trust and honesty. This made ones work more meaningful and fulfilling. It teaches us that the pride we feel in our achievements comes with integrity with which we earned them.

As a busy person, being honest and responsible amid several obligations such as homework that requires for in-depth research, careful composition, and expressing thoughts with others has been put to test. Taking shortcuts to save time is quite tempting, particularly when there are short deadlines. Sometimes, the temptation seemed too much to bear. But, one idea keep reminding me during those moments: The sense of fulfillment that comes from knowing that I gave my all is the greatest reward and the most important thing is to always be truthful and honest.

By using the principles of personal accountability and responsibility that we studied in class, I was able to overcome these challenges. In order to avoid cramming the tasks, I focused on improving my time management. As part of intellectual humility, I also learn to be more open to criticism. The subject taught me to take my limitations as opportunities for growth and improvement rather than as weaknesses. I became better and more trustworthy person as a result of this thinking.

Practicing academic integrity is one of the most fulfilling things you can do. It's the result of investing genuine effort into all of your work. Being dishonest in the academic world invalidates every achievement you've made, and it erodes the trust that holds our scholarly community together. In the future, I will always apply these lessons. I will continue to share this knowledge with my students and colleagues, inspiring them to raise their own legacies of integrity. I will always practice academic integrity myself and serve as an example of the values I cherish. This subject gave me more than just a completion; it has given me a light for my career and a lifelong commitment to being a better, more trustworthy person.

